

Article Arrival Date**13.01.2026****Article Published Date****27.06.2026****Farmers Level of Satisfaction with Agricultural Extension Service and Its Determinant:
In Case of Tenta Woreda, South Wollo Amhara Region, Ethiopia****Workie Sahlu ANBAW¹, Moges Girmay PHOGELLA², Mulugeta AMSALU³**^{1,2,3}Department of Rural Development and Agricultural Extension, College of Agriculture and Natural Resources, Mekdela Amba University, P.O. Box 32, Tuluawlia, Ethiopia**Abstract**

The degree to which smallholder farmers are satisfied with the agricultural extension services they get varies. Such diversity among farmers may be attributed to a range of economic, social, personal, psychological, and institutional factors. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to evaluate farmers' satisfaction levels with agricultural extension services and to examine the factors that influence farmers' satisfaction with agricultural extension services in Tenta district. A multi-stage sampling procedure was used to choose the 193 sample households in total. A structured interview schedule was developed, pre-tested, and used for collecting the essential quantitative data. Descriptive statistics such as mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum, was used. In relation to statistical tests, one way ANOVA, F-value and Chi-square were applied. Results of the study indicated that the most common types of agricultural extension services provided to farmers in the study area are post-harvest handling, soil and water management, input delivery services, land preparation techniques, fertilizer application techniques, pesticide application techniques, irrigation techniques, and livestock production. The satisfaction level results indicated that majority of respondents were moderately satisfied with existing agricultural extension services in area. Moreover, results of ordered logit model indicated that education level of the household, family size, access to information; livestock holding of household in TLU and land size were significantly influenced farmers level of satisfaction with existing agricultural extension services. Based on the findings, provision of information in local language and strengthening adult education are essential recommendations to increase farmers' satisfaction with agricultural extension services.

Key words: Extension Service, Ordered Logit, Tenta, and Satisfaction Level.**1. INTRODUCTION****1.1. Background of the study**

Ethiopia is the second most populous African nation next to Nigeria with a population size of over 94 million (CSA, 2017). The country's economy is mainly dependent on subsistence agriculture which provides 46% of the gross domestic product (GDP) and about 80% of employment. Different studies indicate that low productivity, food insecurity, lack of access to improved seeds, and poor information mechanisms are among the major challenges that the sector has faced for decades (Kassem, 2015). In doing so, the Ethiopian government adopted agricultural extension as a national intervention strategy which is a major component of the

country's development principle called Agricultural Development Led Industrialization (Ministry of Finance and economic Development, 2003).

The agricultural extension system is essential in developing countries to complement traditional agricultural practices through research, information exchange, innovation, and the transfer of agricultural technologies (Issahaku, 2014; Kasem, 2015). Various forms of agricultural extension services exist worldwide. Moreover, agricultural extension services play a profound role in sustainable agricultural development. As environmental degradation, rapid population growth, and unfair trade relations continue to persist in most developing countries, effective extension systems are required that take into consideration the ecological, cultural, social, and economic features of sustainable agriculture. Studies conducted in Kenya and Nepal have shown that the lack of proper agricultural extension services was one of the factors that contributed significantly to rural poverty (Suvedi & Ghimire, 2015; Davis & Place, 2014).

The extension system in Ethiopia has focused on the distribution of standard packages such as seeds and fertilizer, the credit needed to buy inputs, livestock, and training for farmers. This means that the necessary agricultural inputs, advice, and technical support are part of the agricultural production system in the country, where development agents and farmers are the key actors (Hamilton, 2023).

Farmers' agricultural extension service satisfaction is typically based on the direct extension service interaction between the farmer and the organization or its agents in enhancing farmers' loyalty and confidence, extension feedback becoming paramount (Azikiwe et al., 2013). Specifically, the same concept provided by (FUFA, 2018) defines satisfaction as the fulfillment of certain prior expectations related to a product or service.

An excellent agricultural extension and advisory service practice includes technology transfer, human resource development to improve rural livelihoods, building social capital or organizing producer groups, and sustainable natural resource management (water use management, soil and land use management, and integrated pest management) (Mulugeta Tegegn, 2018). In many rural settings, access to adequate knowledge, improved technology, financial services, and other relevant social services remains a critical issue. However, there are still significant challenges in providing Extension and Advisory Services (EAS) in these areas, as demonstrated by (Agegnehu, 2020).

Indeed, (Arias, 2013) also found that poor extension services were ranked as the top reason for farmers' agricultural extension services dissatisfaction. In Ethiopia, lack of quality and diversified improved seeds, limited technology choices, high price of inputs (chemical fertilizer, improved seed) and inconvenient loan system and undefined boundary between extension service and the local politics are the top reasons for farmers dissatisfaction with the extension service (Elias et al., 2015).

Some studies have been conducted in different parts of the country to identify determinants of farmers' satisfaction with agricultural extension services (Elias et al., 2015). However, previous studies have focused on determinants of farmers' satisfaction with agricultural extension services and the factors affecting farmers' satisfaction with agricultural extension services are location specific. While these studies are importance to the researcher, they never addressed the level of farmers' satisfaction with current agricultural extension service, hence a knowledge gap. It is this gap that the study sought to fill.

In addition to that in the study area there is no empirical document on level of farmers' satisfaction with current agricultural extension service and its determinant in Amhara regional state particularly in the study area. This requires some level of investigation via appropriate

research methods to identify farmers' level of satisfaction with the current agricultural extension service in the study area.

Therefore, this study was designed and conducted in the study area to identify agricultural extension services and factors influencing farmers' satisfaction with existing agricultural extension services provision in Tenta district Amhara regional state Ethiopia.

2. MATERIALAND METHODS

2.1. Description of the study area

Tenta woreda is located in the south wollo zone of the Amhara national regional state, about 529 km northeast of Addis Ababa. The woreda is bordered by Delanta and Ambassel woredas in the north, Legambo woreda in the south, Dessie zuria and Kutaber woredas in the east, and Mekdela and Sayint woredas in the west. The woreda comprises 31 rural kebeles and 2 rural towns; Adjibar is the capital town of the woreda. All weather gravel roads connect the zonal capital Dessie with the woreda capital Adjibar; in addition, 13 kebeles are connected by dry weather roads, and 16 kebele are connected by all weathered gravel roads.

According to the CSA, the woreda population is 183,622 (male = 90,506 and female = 93,116). Of the total population in the woreda, about 172,071 (male = 84,811 and female = 87,260) and 11,551 (male = 5696 and female = 5855) are in rural and urban areas, respectively. There are a total of 43,823 households, of which 26.5% are female-headed.

2.2. Study population, sampling method, and sample size

Three randomly chosen kebeles within the study district comprise the **3987** farm households (**3120 male and 867 female**) headed households. It is necessary to use strong methodological principles in order to obtain accurate data and create a sample that more accurately represents the full population. To achieve research objectives, multi-stage sampling techniques were used to select targets for this part of the study. **In the first stage**, Tenta District was selected out of 11 woreda under the current administrative structure in west Wollo Zone in the Amhara Regional State on a purposeful basis; this was done because there was a **dearth of scientific** research on the topic and issues with the adoption of agricultural extension packages. **In the second stage**, three kebelles were selected by using simple random sampling techniques from a total of 33 rural kebelles in the Tenta woreda. **In the third stage**, household heads were selected by using a simple random sampling technique in the three sample kebelles. The reason for using simple random sampling is that there are the same extension services in all kebelles in the district. Then a probability-proportional-to-size sampling technique will be used to draw the sample from each sample kebele.

This study applied a simplified formula provided by Yamane (1967) because it suggested the possibility of using a precision level of ± 3 , ± 5 , ± 7 , and ± 10 as a decimal. In this study, a precision level of ± 7 was chosen because it could yield a sufficient sample size and suit the time and budget constraints.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

$$\frac{3987}{1 + 3987(0.07)^2} = 193$$

Where

- n is the sample size.
- N is the population size.
- e is the level of precision.

2.3. Types and Sources of Data

To fulfill objectives of the study, primary and secondary sources of information were collected from both qualitative and quantitative data. Primary data were gathered from 193 sample households which were related to demographic characteristics, socio economic, institutional, Psychological and factors that were expected to impact farm household's satisfaction level with agricultural extension services provision and type of agricultural extension services offered to farm household, extension methods used to deliver services and others relevant data to the study were obtained from primary sources quantitatively through interview schedule, group discussion, and key informants interview.

All secondary data were gathered through reviewing secondary sources such as research reports, articles, and other documents and publications from woreda agricultural and natural resource development offices and other published and unpublished documents from different sources.

2.4. Method of Data Collection

Based on the nature of the objective and the nature of the research questions, the study combines both qualitative data, such as focus groups and key informant interviews, and quantitative household survey methods to better understand the factors that influence farmers' satisfaction with agricultural extension services.

Six key informants were interviewed, including district extension experts and development agents assigned to the Kebelles, as well as members of the local public media. **Focus group discussions** were held with 16 respondents from three sampled kebeles (10 men and 6 women), who were divided into three groups, one for each kebele.

The group discussions mainly focused on constraints that limit farmers' satisfaction with agricultural extension services, types of extension services offered for farmers, and extension methods used to offer extension services to the farm households.

2.5. Methods of Data Analysis

In this study, quantitative data was analyzed using various descriptive statistics and econometric models appropriate to the data's nature. The qualitative data gathered through key informant interviews and focus group discussions (FGDs) will be presented in the form of statements or narration. Frequently, the response variable can have more than two outcomes, and very often these outcomes are ordinal in nature; that is, they cannot be expressed on an interval scale. These are ordinal scales in that there is a clear ranking among the categories, but to study phenomena such as the preceding, one can extend the bivariate logit and probit models to take into account multiple ranked categories (Gujarati, 1995). The nature of the dependent variables usually determines which model is used. The dependent variable in this study is categorical and ordered. As a result, the ordered logit regression model is appropriate for this study. The ordered logit model is a logistic regression model for an ordinal response variable. The model is used widely to analyze ranked responses (Hensher, 2010). Questions relating to satisfaction with life assessment and expectations are usually ordinal in nature (Anderson & Feder, 2004). Hence, this study employed an ordered logit model to test the degree of the

relationship and determine the relative influence of various explanatory variables on the dependent variable.

The values of Y (the dependent variable) represent the ordered values that represent the level of satisfaction of farmers with extension service, defined as:

- 0: not satisfied**
- Yi= 1: moderately satisfied**
- 2: satisfied**

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Provided Agricultural Extension Services and How They Are Delivered to Farmers

3.1.1 Types of Agricultural Extension Services Delivered in the Study Area

Farmers in the study area have benefited from various agricultural extension services offered by the woreda agricultural resource office via kebele extension workers. The various services that extension workers provide in a given area are made up of various components, the majority of which are challenging to measure. Nonetheless, the kinds of extension services provided can be identified given the study area's context. The study's findings regarding the services provided to farmers in the study area by agricultural extension are covered in this topic.

Table 1's result showed that post-harvest handling, soil and water management, input delivery services, land preparation techniques, fertilizer application techniques, planting techniques, weeding practice techniques, pesticide application techniques, irrigation techniques, and information sharing about new technology were the most common types of agricultural extension services provided to farmers in the study area.

Table 1: Types of Agricultural extension services delivered in the study area

Delivered Extension Services					
		Not Satisfied (N=59)	Moderately Satisfied (N=81)	Satisfied (N=53)	
Post-Harvest Handling	Never	28.81	43.21	45.28	39.38
	Sometimes	45.76	38.27	35.85	39.90
	Commonly	25.42	18.52	18.87	20.73
Total		100%	100%	100%	100%
Soil And Water Management	Never	28.81	25.93	24.53	26.42
	Sometimes	30.51	34.57	41.51	35.23
	Commonly	40.68	39.51	33.96	38.34
Total		100%	100%	100%	100%
Information	Never	15.25	16.05	28.30	19.17

About Better Farming	Sometimes	32.20	24.69	24.53	26.94
	Commonly	52.54	59.26	47.17	53.89
Total		100%	100%	100%	100%
Input Provision	Never	20.34	17.28	16.98	18.13
	Sometimes	38.98	29.63	39.62	35.23
	Commonly	40.68	53.09	43.40	46.63
Total		100%	100%	100%	100%
Row Planting Techniques	Never	11.86	14.81	16.98	14.51
	Sometimes	30.51	33.33	20.75	29.02
	Commonly	57.63	51.85	62.26	56.48
Total		100%	100%	100%	100%
Fertilizer Application	Never	16.95	25.93	22.64	22.28
	Sometimes	20.34	22.22	30.19	23.83
	Commonly	62.71	51.85	47.17	53.89
Total		100%	100%	100%	100%
Land Preparation	Never	27.12	27.16	30.19	27.98
	Sometimes	42.37	40.74	18.87	35.23
	Commonly	30.51	32.10	50.94	36.79
Total		100%	100%	100%	100%
Irrigation Techniques	Never	40.68	32.10	26.42	33.16
	Sometimes	27.12	34.57	39.62	33.68
	Commonly	32.20	233.33	33.96	33.16
Total		100%	100%	100%	100%
Weeding and Management	Never	22.03	17.28	15.09	18.13
	Sometimes	33.90	29.63	28.30	30.57
	Commonly	44.07	53.09	56.60	51.30
Total		100%	100%	100%	100%
Pesticide	Never	23.73	28.40	30.19	27.46

Application Techniques	Sometimes	25.42	37.04	16.98	27.98
	Commonly	50.85	34.57	52.83	44.56
Total		100%	100%	100%	100%
Market Price	Never	61.02	49.38	43.40	51.30
	Sometimes	28.81	35.80	32.08	32.64
	Commonly	10.17	14.81	24.53	16.06
Total		100%	100%	100%	100%

Source: Own Survey Data, 2023(N=193).

The level of satisfaction among respondents with agricultural extension services varies. The most widely available agricultural extension services are those that deal with soil and water management, better farming information, input provision, row planting techniques, fertilizer application, land preparation, and pesticide application techniques.

Qualitative interview results showed that fertilizers increase soil productivity and yield high yields per hectare. From a user's story in the study area, the following provides a very clear explanation of this:

I have been using inputs like fertilizer since 1998. Fertilizer has improved yields and boosted agricultural productivity. For instance, I never used fertilizer until 1998. There were only six quarts of wheat produced per hectare. On the other hand, wheat yield rose from six to fifteen Quintal/hectare after I added fertilizer. I was supplying crops to the market as a result. However, we currently face two significant issues with fertilizer: its exorbitant cost and the lack of availability within the woreda. Because of this, I have decided to use chemical fertilizer below the recommended rate.

3.2 Extension methods for providing extension services

Extension techniques are efficient ways to communicate information and skills so that farmers, who are the intended audience, can readily see, hear, and understand what extension workers are trying to teach them. However, farmers are often blamed for poor adoption of extension services, and success or failure is based on the level of adoption without considering the effectiveness of extension delivery mechanisms (Kassem, 2015). As a result, farmers are informed about the new agricultural policies and practices through the use of extension services. According to Table 3.2's study results, farm/home visits and public meetings were regularly employed in the study area as extension strategies to provide farmers with agricultural extension services.

Figure 1: Extension methods used for extension service delivery

Source: Own Survey Data, 2023 (N = 193)

The result in figure 1 above showed that the majority of respondents indicated meeting, office visit, and farm visit extension methods frequently used by extension agents to deliver extension services, and some respondents indicated sometimes and never used those types of extension methods. On the other hand, the majority of respondents indicated that on farm demonstrations and field days, contact extension methods were sometimes used. While most respondents indicated that group discussion, model farmer visits, and telephone extension methods never used extension methods to deliver extension services for farmers in the study area,

Focus group discussions provide additional confirmation of these results. Field days, training, oral instruction at religious institutions, demonstrations at FTC and at the farms of model farmers, and demonstrations are just a few of the methods that extension workers use to teach and share technologies with farmers.

3.2. The degree of farmers' satisfaction with agricultural extension services

Degree of farmers' satisfaction with provided extension services in this study, refers to the category constructed based on farmers satisfaction index.

A total of sixteen item statements were created, and respondents were asked to respond to formulated questions.

The overall index of farmers' extension services satisfaction is identified on mean frequency obtained from 16 item questions by using Farmers' Satisfaction index (FS) by (Mwamakimbula & Acker, 2014). In one scenario, respondents who received a total score of **25–50 points** from all item statements were interpreted as **dissatisfied** with the current

agricultural extension services; those who received a total score of **51–75 points** were interpreted as somewhat (moderately) satisfied; and those who received a score of **76 or higher** were interpreted as satisfied with the current agricultural extension services.

The real average score for satisfaction with extension services is 61.68, with a standard deviation of 18.40. The lowest and highest scores are 26.56 and 96.87, respectively. The extension services satisfaction categories were calculated on the basis of the mean and standard deviation. Accordingly, the result in Table and chart 3.2 showed that the total score was computed from satisfaction item statements to identify the satisfaction categories of respondents.

Figure 2: Frequency distribution of extension services satisfaction level of farmers

Source: Own Survey Data, 2023 (N = 193)

According to the study results in the above figure 2 the majority of respondents (41.97%) were moderately satisfied with the provided agricultural extension services, followed by 30.57% who were not satisfied with the provided agricultural extension services and 27.46% who were satisfied with the provided agricultural extension services in the study area. According to the study findings, the majority of farmers in the study area are moderately satisfied with the current agricultural extension services provided by extension organizations.

3.3. Factors that Influence Farmers' Satisfaction with Agricultural Extension Services

The ordered logit regression model was found to contain a total of 12 explanatory variables (Table 2). Seven (7) of those variables were found to have no significant impact on the likelihood of farmers being satisfied with agricultural extension services.

These include the household's age, gender, distance from the farmer training center, credit availability, cooperative membership, training accessibility, and type of extension services. It also showed that five (5) variables, including family size, land size, education level, and

livestock holding (TLU), significantly influenced the likelihood that farmers would be satisfied with agricultural extension services.

Table 2: The ML Estimates of the Ordered Logit Model

Variables	Odds Ratio	Std. Err.	Z	P>z
Sex HH	.7950165	.3153871	-0.58	0.563
Education level	2.004512	.743064	1.88	0.061*
Age HH	1.006296	.0208397	-0.30	0.762
Farm size	3.498235	.8917378	4.91	0.000***
Family size	1.542511	.1941978	3.44	0.001***
Distance to FTC	.8247428	.270656	-0.59	0.557
Livestock in TLU	2.898708	.7580789	4.07	0.000***
Access to credit	1.624332	.5800125	1.36	0.174
Cooperative membership	1.317014	.466163	0.78	0.437
Access to training	.6960088	.2373229	-1.06	0.288
Access to information	1.798149	.6148687	1.72	0.086*
Nature of extension Services	1.20532	.4475079	0.50	0.615
Number of obs = 193		Prob > chi2 = 0.0000		
LR chi2(11) = 153.12		Pseudo R2 = 0.3683		

Source: Own Survey Data, Model Output 2023 (N = 193), *, **, and * significant at 1%, 5%, and 10% probability levels, respectively**

Based on the ordered logit model result in **Table 2** the interpretation of each statistically significant explanatory variable with their relative influence on farmers' satisfaction with agricultural extension services were discussed as follows.

Education level (Educlevel): The ordered logit model output indicates that, at a 10% significant level, respondents' education level has a positive and significant impact on farmers' satisfaction with agricultural extension services. The positive sign of education level of respondents indicates that as education level increases, the tendency of farmers' satisfaction with agricultural extension service also increases. Farmers with higher levels of education and literacy are better able to use extension materials and agricultural information, adopt technology more easily, and search for and utilize it. For literate households compared to illiterate households, the likelihood of being satisfied with the agricultural extension service is 2.00 times higher. This is consistent with the findings of (Abate & Shiferaw, 2011).

Family Size (Famsa): Based on the results of the econometric ordered logit model, it is observed that, at a probability of less than 1% significant level, the number of family sizes positively and significantly influences farmers' satisfaction with agricultural extension services. The result is agreed with what was hypothesized to be. This implies that, households' interest and motivation to search or get new information as well as their frequency participation in different information source could be increased. The probability of being satisfied with the agricultural extension service is 1.54 times greater for respondents who have large family size than others consistent with the findings of (Mulugeta Tegegn, 2018).

Farm land size (Farmsa): When farmers are ready to adopt new technology, the availability of an appropriate farm size is critical. Farm size is related to farmers' satisfaction with agricultural extension services and is significant at the 1% level. Other variables being constant, a one-hectare increase in land size increases farmers' satisfaction by a factor of 3.49 in comparison to the base category. This finding is in line with the findings of Berhanu Gebremedhin (2006). They concluded that those farmers with larger land sizes per hectare, whether a single parcel or several parcels were more satisfied than those with smaller land sizes per hectare, which may be related to the commodities produced and extension services provided.

Livestock Holding of Household (TLU): Farmers' satisfaction with agricultural extension services was positively impacted by household livestock holding at a significant level less than 1%. Farmers who own a larger number of livestock in TLU are more likely to be satisfied with agricultural extension services than respondents who own fewer livestock, as indicated by the positive parameter estimate sign.

The implication is that owners of large number of livestock in TLU are often rich, have access to more resources, including extension information, and can better afford risk. Other variable held constant, for a one unit increase tropical livestock unit cause farmers' satisfaction level with agricultural extension services score to be increases by the factor of 2.89 in reference to base category. This result is in consistent with the finding of (Daniel Ayalew Ali, 2012). In Ethiopian agriculture, livestock is a significant source of food, cash, and draught power for crop cultivation.

Access to Information (Accesinfo): At the 10% significant level, the results of an ordered logit model show a significant and positive relationship between farmers' satisfaction with agricultural extension services and access to information. The estimated coefficient of access to information's positive sign suggests that respondents with access to information are more likely to be satisfied than those without. Better access to agricultural information makes farmer to take appropriate decisions on problem facing them and answer questions faced in their daily lives regarding to agricultural activities which in turn improves quality and yield of products and enable to get better price. As by one unit change in Access to information by respondents, cause farmers' satisfaction level with agricultural extension services score to be increases by the factor of 1.79 in reference to base category. Producers that have contact with technological information can improve their production more efficiently than those who are not (Alemayehu Keba Musba Kedir, 2020).

4. CONCLUSION

This paper was aimed at clarifying farmers' satisfaction level with provided extension services and to analyze determinants of farmers' satisfaction level with the existing extension service provision in in Tenta district south Wollo Ethiopia. The results of the study can be concluded procedural as follows;

The research result revealed that the majority of farmers' were in moderate level of satisfaction with provided agricultural extension services. Result implying that, the extension program in study area has needed an improvement to some extent. Farming is the backbone of the farmers and as such, it is important to agricultural development that most farmers are fully satisfied with the existing agricultural extension service provision. Fully satisfied farmers are likely to be more productive and more cooperative with government's plans and additionally, this could positively impact on food security and in country GDP.

The empirical results of ordered logit model revealed that below mentioned variables were significant and positive influence on farmers' satisfaction with agricultural extension services. Those were perceived education level of respondents at less than 10% probability level, farm land size at less than 1% probability level, family size at less than 1% probability level, access to information at less than 10% probability level, TLU (livestock holding of household) at less than 1% probability level increases farmers' satisfaction with the agricultural extension services.

A well-developed, long-term plan to finance and provide extension services is necessary for the growth and development of farmers' agriculture. Other requirements include motivated and skilled development agents, advanced and well-equipped FTCs, and well-established methods for providing extension services. Therefore, it is possible to enhance the provision of agricultural extension services by implementing pluralistic extension service methods, offering extension services that are driven by demand, and enhancing the financial performance of farmers with the help of the Tenta Woreda administration and the South Wollo Zone Agricultural Office.

Declarations

Consent for publication

All the primary data has been anonymized. Besides, informed consent was obtained from all the participant respondents through an informed consent form.

Availability of data and materials

Data will be made available upon reasonable request.

Conflicts of interest or competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Financial Interest

Authors' contributions

All authors contributed to the conception, approach, research, oversight, evaluation, data curation, analysis, drafting, and editing.

Workie Sahlu was involved in literature search, figures, development of overall research plan, study design, data collection, data analysis, data interpretation hypothesis generation and idea development, provided the validated questionnaires.

Moges Girmay and Mulugeta Amsalu were involved in data collection, data analysis, data interpretation, supervision, data analysis and revision of the paper; and she wrote the paper.

The authors declare that they have no any financial interests

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